

DISEASE BRIEF RIFT VALLEY FEVER

	Characteristics	Description
1	Disease and Pathogen	<p>Rift Valley fever (RVF) is a mosquito-borne disease which affects animals (domestic and wild ruminants and camels) and humans. The disease can be transmitted by a wide spectrum of mosquitos, the most relevant being the <i>Aedes</i> and <i>Culex</i> genus. RVF virus (RVFV) is a single-stranded RNA virus of the genus <i>Bunyaviridae</i>.</p> <p>In humans, the disease ranges from a mild flu-like illness to severe haemorrhagic fever that can be lethal. When livestock are infected, the disease can cause significant economic losses due to high mortality rates in young animals and waves of abortions in pregnant females. (1)</p>
2	Regulatory status in the EU	<p>RVF is a WOAAH-notifiable disease.</p> <p>RVF is listed in Regulation (EU) 2016/429, Reg (EU) 2018/1882, Reg (EU) 2020/2002, Reg (EU)2020/687.</p> <p>Co/financed programmes: European Union's Horizon Europe programme for vaccine development and multiannual programmes of training and workshops for crisis preparedness.</p>
3	Geographical distribution (of autochthonous cases)	<p>In Western, Eastern and Southern Africa (including Madagascar) and several Indian Ocean islands RVF is endemic.</p> <p>RVF has also been reported in Egypt and the Arabic peninsula where animal and human outbreaks have taken place. (2)</p>
4	Reservoir / main host	<p>Reservoirs: Wildlife hosts, mainly ruminants, may act as a reservoir during the inter-epidemic periods (sylvatic cycle). Mosquitoes (<i>Aedes</i> sp. diapausing eggs) are also considered as reservoirs, even though this has only been demonstrated under laboratory conditions. In Africa, RVFV has been found in some species of rodents, bats and even non-human primates.</p> <p>Serological positive findings have been detected in several animal species. However, the significance of these findings is still unknown.</p>

5	Host range / susceptible species (domestic / wild)	RVF affects domestic and wild ruminants and camels.
6	Vector-borne transmission	<p>The principal vectors of RVF are mosquitos, mainly <i>Aedes</i>, <i>Culex</i> and, to a lesser degree, <i>Anopheles</i>. Other arthropods such as biting midges or ticks are indicated as candidates for mechanical vectors.</p> <p>Main potential RVF mosquito vectors within the EU are: <i>Aedes albopictus</i>, <i>Aedes caspius</i>, <i>Aedes detritus</i>, <i>Aedes japonicus</i>, <i>Aedes vexans</i>, <i>Culex pipiens</i> and <i>Culex theileri</i>.</p> <p>As reported by Wint et al., 2020, all EU member states harbor RVF vectors in their territory (3; 4).</p>
7	Environmental transmission	No.
8	(Main) transmission routes to domestic animals	Through competent mosquito vectors.
9	(Main) transmission routes to humans	<p>Humans are usually infected through direct or indirect contact with infected livestock. They can also be infected through bites from infected mosquitoes. There is also evidence that supports the possible infection via the consumption of unpasteurized or unboiled milk of infected animals.</p> <p>To date, no human-to-human transmission of RVFV has been documented, and no transmission of RVF to health care workers has been reported when standard infection control precautions have been put in place. Abattoir workers that are occupationally exposed to infectious material from potentially RVF-infected animals have been proposed as a useful sentinel population for surveillance of RVF (5).</p>
10	Disease indicators	
11	a) Clinical signs	Clinical signs vary depending on the virulence of the virus strain and the species, breed and age of the affected animals. Clinical signs range from mild, non-specific symptoms to sudden death or abortion. Mortality in lambs and kids can reach 70–100% while in sheep and calves it can amount to 20–70%. Affected

		herd experience rates of 85–100% of abortions. Camels usually have an inapparent infection, otherwise asymptomatic infections are rare (except for humans).
12	b) Seroconversion	The presence of a certain level of seropositivity in animals in areas where the disease has never been reported has been described. It should, however, be noted that these reports are the result of studies with limited sample sizes, areas of study and where the data on animal origin was lacking. The countries where such a situation was reported are Turkey, Tunisia, Iran, Iraq, Algeria and Western Sahara.
13	c) Other disease indicators	Abundance of mosquito vectors. Climate indicators: epizootic transmission is favored by particular climatic conditions, such as heavy rains, warm weather and increased greenness of vegetation index.
14	Indicators relevant for monitoring (Indicator-based surveillance)	Mortality in lambs, kids and calves. Abortions in all ruminants.
15	Test systems available for infection/disease detection	<p>Identification of RVFV:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Virus isolation; - Antigen-detection enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA); - Immunopathology. <p>Viral RNA detection:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) – Gold standard; - Nested RT-PCR method; - Quantitative real-time PCR; - Multiplex PCR-based microarray assay; - RT Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (RT-LAMP); - Recently, a pen-side test for early detection of viraemic animals has been developed; <p><u>Samples:</u> whole blood or serum samples during the febrile stage of the disease, or from organs (e.g., liver, spleen and brain)</p>

		<p>tissues) of animals that have died and from the organs of aborted fetuses. RVFV can also be detected in milk.</p> <p>Isolations are usually made on cell cultures such as African green monkey kidney (Vero), baby hamster kidney (BHK) cells and sucking mice.</p> <p>Serological tests:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ELISA = cannot distinguish between past and acute RVFV infections; - Virus neutralisation test (VNTs) = gold standard for detecting previous exposure to RVFV. <p><u>Samples:</u> Serum and milk.</p> <p>According to WHO recommendations, definitive diagnosis of RVFV infection requires: (1) detection of virus RNA in serum or plasma via real-time polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR); (2) detection of anti-RVFV IgM and IgG antibodies; (3) detection of RVFV virus antigen and/or (4) RVFV isolation.</p> <p>There is currently (2022) one OIE Reference Laboratory for Rift-Valley fever in Europe - CIRAD, France (6).</p>
16	Surveillance component options (+ rationale)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Indicator-based surveillance of abortion and increased mortality in young stock in ruminants 2. Bulk milk surveillance in ruminants in high-risk areas and season 3. Pathogen detection in mosquitoes in areas of introduction risk <p>If RVFV is introduced into a naive ruminant population, a high incidence of clinical signs in ruminants is expected. Therefore, a surveillance with focus on the clinical signs abortion and mortality of young stock would be the most promising and cost-effective method for early detection of disease introduction. Bulk milk serology can be a good option to detect virus introduction before it causes massive clinical signs in animals and may also reduce the risk of a large human outbreaks. Because the most likely route of introduction is via infected vectors, surveillance of vectors is another good method to</p>

		<p>support early detection in high-risk areas (Southern European countries close to endemic areas, regions around major airports and ports).</p> <p>RVF may pose a risk for endangered wildlife species in Europe. Among wild endangered species distributed in Europe potentially infected by RVFV (diagnosis includes direct detection of pathogen), classified according of their conservation status according (International Union for the Conservation of Nature), 40,6% species are "Near Threatened", 40,6% are "Vulnerable", 12,5% Endangered, and 6,2% Critically Endangered (CR) (7).</p>																																										
		<p style="text-align: center;">Component name</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2">VECTOR-borne diseases</th> <th>GENERAL POPULATION</th> <th>EXPOSED</th> <th>INFECTED</th> <th>INFECTIOUS</th> <th>SYMPTOMATIC</th> <th>GP/ND/VISIT</th> <th>DEAD</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td rowspan="4">Rift Valley Fever (RVF)</td> <td>Ruminants</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mosquitoes</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Human</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Indicator-based surveillance of abortion and increased mortality in young stock in ruminants Bulk milk surveillance in ruminants in high-risk areas and season Pathogen detection in mosquitoes in areas of introduction risk Surveillance components targeting human were not in scope</p>	VECTOR-borne diseases		GENERAL POPULATION	EXPOSED	INFECTED	INFECTIOUS	SYMPTOMATIC	GP/ND/VISIT	DEAD	Rift Valley Fever (RVF)	Ruminants								Mosquitoes								Human															
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17	Comparison of surveillance component options (main advantages/disadvantages)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Indicator-based surveillance can be performed on the whole ruminant population of Europe with a small investment of resources. Many EU MS already have a surveillance of abortions and increased mortality in place. The main disadvantage is that the sensitivity of this surveillance component greatly depends on disease awareness and willingness to report. Timeliness of this surveillance component is also not ideal, because disease will only be detected after the personnel of farms with clinical signs has been exposed; Bulk milk can be collected relatively easily and is already used in other surveillance systems such as Bluetongue surveillance. However, serological tests are not validated for bulk milk testing, so the sensitivity of this surveillance component might be low. 																																										

		Surveillance of vectors is the best option for timely detection of virus introduction. It is the only surveillance component which potentially allows detection of introduction before exposure of humans. Surveillance can be combined with other vector surveillance.
18	Countries which already carry out surveillance for this pathogen	For 2019, 22 MS had a surveillance system for human disease in place. This was mostly based on passive surveillance by notifications of physicians, hospitals and laboratories. Czechia and Slovakia reported active surveillance in humans. For animals, there is no current EU legislation or diagnostic manual for the early detection or surveillance.
19	References	<p>1) https://www.who.int/health-topics/rift-valley-fever#tab=tab_1</p> <p>2) https://wahis.woah.org/#/dashboards/country-or-disease-dashboard</p> <p>3) Wint W., Petric D., Van Bortel W., Schaffner F., 2020. RVF vector spatial distribution models: Vector Abundance. EFSA supporting publication 2020: EN-1847. 35 pp. doi:10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1847</p> <p>4) https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/disease-vectors/surveillance-and-disease-data/mosquito-maps</p> <p>5) Al-Azraqi, Tarik., 2013. Exposure of abattoirs workers to rift valley fever virus infection in Southwestern Saudi Arabia. Open Journal of Preventive Medicine. 03. 28-31. 10.4236/ojpm.2013.31004.</p> <p>6) https://www.woah.org/en/what-we-offer/expertise-network/reference-laboratories/#ui-id-3</p> <p>7) ENETWILD-consortium, Klaas, Marina, Sebastian, Mario, Ferroglio, Ezio, Goncalves, Catarina, Vada, Rachele, Vicente, Joaquín, Zanet, Stefania, Dolores-Gavier-Widén, , Vicente, Joaquín. 2022. A review of endangered wildlife hosts in Europe for selected pathogens to be targeted by One Health surveillance. EFSA Supporting publication 2022: 19(12):EN-7766. 12 pp. doi:10.2903/sp.efsa.2022.EN-7766</p>